

REVIEW OF RESEARCH

International Online Multidisciplinary Journal

Volume - IV Special Issue ISSN : 2249-894X Nov - 2019

Peer Reviewed Referred

ज्ञान-विज्ञान विमुक्तये

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	LAXMI
	BOOK PUBLICATION, Solapur
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International Online Multidisciplinary Journal

Volume - 4 Special Issue ISSN : 2249-894X Nov - 2019

Peer Reviewed Journal
Journal No. 48514

IMPACT FACTOR – 5.8
www.sjifactor.com

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Understanding the Criteria for Measuring Quality of Work-life and Causes of Stress

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Abstract

Every person should contribute every-day for improving life and job as well as career or business context in the world. In present days only few peoples only get in good career in the competitive world. Then others get have get opportunity in based on knowledge and skills. Here in this articles presents about the Quality of work life and measures to improve the QWL and also issues of stress and motivation. Quality of work life represents not only employees and for employers and organization and it is includes with job satisfaction, job involvement, job motivation, job stress etc. The all the succeed organization is highly think about how to impress the employees within the workplace and motivate, and retains the workforce.

Key words: Quality of work life, Criteria of QWL and Causes of Stress.

Introduction

The Human Resource Management provides the concept of Quality of Work life engaged with various aspects of working environment and which facilitates the human resource development efficiently. The QWL also helps for development of human resources. It includes motivates the employees to learn for present position to future roles. According to **J. Richard and J. Loy**, "QWL is the degree to which members of a work organization are able to satisfy important personal needs through their experiences in the organization". Generally employees will expect in inside of organization like favorable working conditions based their designation. some employees satisfy their role of work life, some employees satisfy their family role but most of employees make confused both life with the reason of frustration, stress and problems of personal life. the reason is the employee would not believe their values. The value means hard work and sincerity. They are not improving them-selves. The employers classify different methods to provide for favorable working conditions for

employees. There has been much concern today about decent wages, convenient working hours, conducive working conditions, transport facilities, safety requirements, and job security etc. their term "Quality of worklife" has appeared in research journals and the press in USA only in 1970's. It refers to favourableness' and unfavourableness' of job environment for people.

Quality of work life

Quality of work life refers to "It is a measurement of identify the employees work life and find the conducive of working environment". It is concerned with improving employee relation and co-operation to solve many organizational problems, achieving the desired level of performance and securing greater employee satisfaction.

Criteria for measuring QWL

Human Resource Management provide the following criteria to measures the degree of QWL:

Sufficient and fair compensation

The method of remuneration payable to the employee must be sufficient and fair. It should provide the employees a reasonable standard of living and should also be comparable to the pay of employees doing same jobs.

Safety and healthful working condition

The employers provide safe and healthy working conditions for their employees due to requirements. This is a way to show care about of employees in the organization. Like health centers, safety equipments, canteens etc.

Chance to utilise and improving human capacities

The work assigned to every employee for improve to work his capabilities. Employees must also have the opportunity to modernize their job knowledge and skill by undergo refresher training.

Better opportunities for career growth

Employees look for every opportunity to move superior positions. Opportunity only prove their self in the workplace. Every employer to provide suitable career opportunities for his employees to secure their loyalty towards the organization.

Social integration in the work force

The working place make a feel about the employees to develop the self-esteem, openness, confidence and trust. They are easily mingle with and colleagues superiors.

Constitutional protection in workplace

The employees should come from under the quality of work life. They must have speech and freedom and should be able to challenge the actions of employer on any matter.

Balance of personal and work life

Quality of work life provides for the impartial relationship among work, non work and family aspects of life. In other words family and social life should not be strained by working including overtime work, work during inconvenient hours, business travel, transfers, vacations.

Social relevance of work

The work of an employee is not seen as a simple economic action in qwl. The employee must be conscious of the social implications his job. He should, therefore, avoid doing anything that is detrimental to the interests of the society of which he is a part.

Stress

A person undergoes stress when he feels that he is ill-equipped to carry out tasks assigned to him. Not everyone under goes stress in a workplace. It is also not possible to clarify exactly the condition that would give span for stress because, lots of individuals are capable of performing their responsibilities irrespective of the work situation .

Total absence of stress may affect performance. A person requirements to suffer a certain level of stress to perform well. Too much stress is harmful. When stress exceeds a certain level, it can have adverse effect on a person's emotions, mind and physical health.

John W. Newstrom and Keith Davis have made the following observations about **stress**

- Stress is the general term applied to the pressures people feel in life.
- The occurrence of stress at job is almost predictable in many jobs.
- human being differences make up a wide range of reactions to stress – a tasks viewed as challenging by one person may produce high levels of anxiety in another.

- When pressures begins to build up, it can cause adverse strain on a person's emotions, thought process and physical condition.
- while stress becomes excessive, employees build up various symptoms that can damage their job presentation and health and even pressure their ability to cope with the situation.

Causes of Stress

The various factors that cause stress can be grouped under :

- Personal factors
- Organizational factors

Personal factors

Personal factors responsible for stress include, among others, the following:

- ❖ Ability
- ❖ Perception
- ❖ Manner of approaching crisis
- ❖ Level of self confidence
- ❖ Experience desire for works
- ❖ Beliefs

Organizational factor :

The organizational factors causing stress include, among others, the following :

- ❖ Nature of job
- ❖ Superior – subordinates relationship
- ❖ Inter-personal relationship
- ❖ Target to be reached
- ❖ Time pressure
- ❖ Physical working conditions
- ❖ Hours of works

The problem of stress is not peculiar to a formal workplace like include social life, friends, and business establishments.

Conclusion

From the above articles, we can identify about the quality of work life and causes of stress plays a major role in the organizations. The employees face more serious problems that causes illness and it affect physically, mentally and emotionally. The personal and professional life of the employees get affected, due to the stress that which causes a major

impact on the quality work life of employees. The Organization must take steps to reduce stress and employee also the knowledge of quality of work life.

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